
ISSUES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES IN THE EDUCATION OF AGRICULTURAL SPECIALISTS.

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This article talks about the importance and extent of the development of professional competence of future agricultural specialists, the introduction of information technologies in their professional activities.

Key words.

Sphere of education, specialist, agricultural sphere, professional activity, competence, professional competence, ability, level of abilities, digital technologies, digitalization, consumers, intellectual farmer.

Entrance department.

The reforms carried out in the education system of our republic require the adaptation of teaching to world standards and the use of the most effective methods. In this regard, it is no secret that significant work is being done in the field of education in our country. Fundamental improvement of the education system, determination of the target areas of training of highly educated specialists, especially continuous improvement of the professional qualifications and knowledge level of pedagogues are among the most urgent issues. Wide use of the achievements of science and innovation activities in the world education system, consistent and stable development of all spheres of society and state life are becoming an important factor in building a worthy future of the country. In countries such as Japan, USA, Finland, South Korea, Russia, China, the training of competitive personnel with high professional competence is considered as the main direction of development, and innovative technologies, including modern, interactive and creative methods of teaching, are widely used in education is provided.

Experts predict that the population will increase by 2 billion by 2050. There is a need to increase the volume of food production so that the world's population does not face the problem of hunger. Therefore, there will be a great demand for agricultural specialists.

Department of Methods

Of course, global changes await the industry. Successful introduction of the latest technologies into production activities eases human labor and makes it possible to increase the efficiency of farms several times. From now on, specialists will have to regularly increase their professional potential to meet the demands of the times, wherever they are in production or in the labor market.

It should be noted that a number of specialties are losing their importance year by year. Specialists who have chosen professions in the field of agriculture may be worried about the decrease in demand for their profession in the future. But many studies show that in the near future the demand for many professions in agriculture and agriculture will increase, which means that a specialist in this field will never be unemployed.

The agro-industrial complex is one of the most important sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan. At the current stage of the agrarian reform, due to the need to get out of the crisis, special requirements are being put forward in personnel policy. In this context, the question of what a mature professional in the field of agriculture should be is relevant. Today, when employers set the requirements for employees, they do not look at the list of subjects taught to the student or grades, but rather on his knowledge, skills and qualifications, that is, in a word, on the level of professional competence are based on.

Results section

The development of information technologies led not only to an increase in the amount of information consumed, but also to its rapid obsolescence and at the same time the need to constantly update it. In such conditions, the effectiveness of professional activity depends not on having the information given once and for all, but on the ability to manage information flows, initiative, ability to solve problems, and the ability to search for and use missing knowledge. The composition of the professional competence of a graduate of the agricultural university includes cognitive-active, motivational-valuable, reflexive-communicative components. Professional competence includes the ability to acquire and improve general professional and special knowledge; leadership, ability to communicate with colleagues, skills in working with documents, information from various sources; skills in developing technological processes, creating production projects, etc. Professional competence means to constantly update knowledge, to acquire new information in a specialty to successfully solve professional problems. Professional competence is aimed at successful work in a certain professional environment, ensuring the quality and reliability of work within the relevant professions.

Thus, taking into account the specific features of agricultural development and the activities of agricultural higher education institutions, in order to achieve good results in the training of specialists, special attention should be paid to the process of professional training, to enrich their professional and communicative experience. Against the crisis of personal and professional mobility of future agricultural specialists, there are elements of introduction of professional qualification improvement system of future agricultural specialists.

The purpose of the unity of these conditions is to solve the general pedagogical task - to train an agricultural specialist oriented to professional activity in his region at the educational institution. When solving the problem of training agricultural specialists, it is necessary to take into account the problem of internal and external means of solving it.

Discussion.

In the formation of educational programs, first of all, it is necessary to determine the goals to be achieved in the process of education and practice, as well as to determine the professionally important components of the activity of specialists, which form the basis of the requirements for professional activity. The goal is to prepare a mature specialist in accordance with the requirements of the time. The personality of the young professional should be oriented towards ethical professional activity aimed at self-realization in the host society. The goals of education and training are determined in accordance with the social demands of the society on the individual's intellectual and value orientations and his professional qualities.

At the same time, it is necessary to change the process of training of future agricultural specialists, which will contribute to the training of specialists who meet the requirements of the new era, aimed at improving the quality of professional and personal competencies of graduates of higher educational institutions.

Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that the concept of "professional development" includes the meaning of organizing the unity of the base of pedagogical conditions purposefully created in educational institutions for the effective development of the skills of future agricultural specialists.

Traditional processes associated with physically heavy and hard work in the field of agriculture are a thing of the past. It is also difficult to imagine modern agriculture without IT technologies. Knowledge of modern information and communication technologies and foreign languages is necessary for successful work and timely acquaintance with world-class achievements in this field. The rapid development of the economy requires professional skills and competitiveness

of workers. These changes inevitably encourage a person to be more responsible in his professional activity.

Conclusion.

Modern society demands in-depth theoretical and practical knowledge in the field of agriculture from the graduates of higher educational institutions of agriculture. The success of the formation and development of civilized, highly developed agricultural production largely depends on their professional skills, personal and social maturity. In addition, along with the level of development of the network, the level of requirements for agricultural specialists is also increasing, which seriously affects the change of the strategy of training specialists. This is especially relevant and important in the field of agriculture, which is acutely experiencing crisis processes.[2]

As the President said, the possibilities of more productive use of the fertile lands of Uzbekistan, which has a fertile and favorable climate, are very wide. After all, if the people and peasants are rich, the state will also be rich. The strategy for the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan is important because it has vital and specific tasks and is aimed at such noble goals.[1]

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